

***N*-Mannich Bases of Salicylamide**

G. B. Singh and S. P. Agrawal

N-Mannich bases of salicylamide, using aliphatic and heterocyclic secondary amines, have been prepared and their mode of formation and mechanism discussed.

Salicylic acid and its derivatives have won therapeutic importance, particularly as analgesic in medicinal chemistry. Salicylamide is a compound having a hydrogen atom of pronounced reactivity and should therefore undergo Mannich condensation. The present communication deals with the Mannich condensation with salicylamide. The preparation of α -aminoalkyl derivatives has been undertaken because in a large variety of compounds, the insertion of an aminomethyl moiety has been found to augment the therapeutic value.

In the preparation of the *N*-Mannich bases, the secondary amines like dimethylamine, diethylamine, dibutylamine, morpholine, piperidine, pyrrolidine, and piperazine were employed.

The reaction was carried out by employing equimolar quantities (0.1M) of salicylamide, dissolved in methanol, formaldehyde solution (38%), and a secondary amine under mild conditions (mixing and stirring the reactants at 0°). In the case of open-chain amines and pyrrolidine, enough hydrochloric acid was added till the reaction was distinctly acidic and the corresponding Mannich bases were obtained as hydrochlorides. In other cases, the free bases were obtained. In most of the cases, the product appeared as crystals after removal of the major portion of the solvent under reduced pressure and keeping it at 0°. The Mannich bases of salicylamide as hydrochloride prepared are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Mannich bases.	*M.P.	Yield. [Theoretical]
I. <i>N</i> -(Dimethylaminomethyl)-S,HCl	110-11°	32%
II. <i>N</i> -(Diethylaminomethyl)-S,HCl	127°	35
III. <i>N</i> -(Dibutylaminomethyl)-S,HCl	92°	48
IV. <i>N</i> -(Piperidinomethyl)-S	130°	55
V. <i>N</i> -(Morpholinomethyl)-S	125-26°	40
VI. <i>N</i> -(Pyrrolidinomethyl)S,HCl	185-87°(d)	11
VII. <i>NN'</i> -Bis-(salicylamidomethyl)piperazine	164-66°(d)	90

*All m.p.s. are uncorrected.
S denotes salicylamide.

Structure of *N*-Mannich Bases of Salicylamide

In the Mannich condensation of salicylamide, the entrant aminomethyl group could occupy any one of the three possible positions:

(a) Like most of the alcohols¹, it might replace phenolic hydrogen atom, yielding *O,N*-acetal.

(b) Like phenols², it could enter the benzene ring, *ortho* to -OH group.

(c) As in the case of benzamide and other primary amides³, the aminomethyl group could replace the amide hydrogen atom, yielding the carboxamido derivatives of salicylamide.

The physical and chemical evidences put forward (*vide infra*) definitely prove that the Mannich bases of salicylamide are the carboxamido derivatives.

All Mannich bases of salicylamide, dissolved in methanol, turn purple on treatment with ferric chloride solution, indicating the presence of phenolic group.

When *N*-(morphelinomethyl)salicylamide is subjected to low-pressure hydrogenolysis in presence of Raney nickel⁴, salicylamide is regenerated, showing that the aminomethyl group enters at the amido-nitrogen.

Geitstein *et al.*⁴ subjected tetracycline, chlorotetracycline, and oxytetracycline to aminomethylation with morpholine, pyrrolidine, dibenzylamine, and formaldehyde in butanol¹. By the use of I. R. absorption spectra and chemical evidence, they established that aminomethylation occurred in the ring A of the tetracycline at -CONH₂ grouping and not in the phenolic ring D⁵. It provides further proof in favour of salicylamide Mannich bases being carboxamide derivatives, since the ring A of tetracycline is very much alike salicylamide.

In the present investigation, the I. R. absorption spectra of two representative compounds, viz., *N*-(piperidinomethyl)salicylamide and *N*-(dibutylaminomethyl)salicylamide

1. Hellmann and Opitz, *Chem. Ber.*, 1956, 89, 81.

2. Reichert, "Die Mannich-Reaction", Springer Verlag, 1959, p. 53.

3. Hellmann and Haas, *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 50.

4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 1198.

5. Siedel *et al.*, *Munchener med. Wochschr.*, 1959, 661.

hydrochloride, were taken along with that of salicylamide. The I.R. spectrum of salicylamide showed bands at 1625K, characteristic of $-\text{CONH}_2$ grouping, and that of N' -(dibutylaminomethyl)salicylamide hydrochloride showed bands at 1614 K and 1650K, characteristic of a mono-substituted amide function. In the case of I.R. spectrum of N' -(piperidinomethyl)salicylamide, the bands were obtained at 1623 K and 1665K, supporting the view that the salicylamide Mannich bases are carboxamido derivatives.

Einhorn⁶ prepared N' -methylol of salicylamide by treating it with formaldehyde under various conditions and after characterising it, he condensed it with a variety of compounds including piperidine, which resulted in the formation of N' -(piperidinomethyl)salicylamide. This definitely points to the reaction mechanism proposed by Zinner and Herbig⁷ in the cases of benzoxazolone and benzimidazolone:

In the first-step, salicylamide combines with formaldehyde to form N' -methylol compound (II) which then further reacts with the secondary amine (HNR_2) to yield the corresponding N' -Mannich base with the elimination of one molecule of water.

*EXPERIMENTAL

N-(Dimethylaminomethyl)salicylamide Hydrochloride.—To a mixture of salicylamide (13.7 g., 0.1M) and dimethylamine hydrochloride (8.15 g, 0.1M) in methanol (130 ml) was added under stirring a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml, 0.1M). It was kept overnight at 5°. About 2/3 of the solvent was removed and the residue was kept at 0°. The white crystals were filtered and recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 110-11°, yield 7.5 g. (32%). The substance is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, and ethyl acetate but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 52.18; H, 5.73; N, 11.85. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 52.06; H, 6.51; N, 12.15%).

N-(Diethylaminomethyl)salicylamide Hydrochloride.—To a solution of salicylamide (13.7g.) in methanol (130 ml) was added diethylamine (7.3 g.). The mixture was well cooled in ice and acidified with HCl (pH ~ 5.0) and then treated with a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml). It was left overnight at 5°. About 2/3 of the solvent was removed and the residue kept at 0° for crystallisation. After filtration the crystals were recrystallised from formamide, m.p. 127°, yield 9 g. (35%). It is soluble in methanol, ethanol, ethyl acetate, acetone, and formamide but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 55.26; H, 7.18; N, 10.70. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 55.71; H, 7.35; N, 10.83%).

N-(Dibutylaminomethyl)salicylamide Hydrochloride.—To dibutylamine (12.9 g.), acidified with HCl, was added a solution of salicylamide (13.7 g.) in methanol (130 ml). Then under cooling and stirring it was treated with a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml).

6. *Annalen*, 1905, 343, 207.

7. *Chem. Ber.*, 1957, 90, 1548; 1956, 89, 81.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method.

The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about 2 hours. On cooling, the crystals appeared which were filtered and dried. The product was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 92°, yield 1.5 g. (48%). It is soluble in methanol, ethanol, ethyl acetate, formamide, and dimethylformamide but only slightly soluble in water. (Found: C, 60.46; H, 8.03; N, 9.29. $C_{16}H_{27}O_2N_2Cl$ requires C, 61.05; H, 8.58; N, 9.78%.)

N-(*Piperidinomethyl*)salicylamide.—Salicylamide (13.7 g.), suspended in water (50 ml), was treated under continuous stirring and cooling with a mixture of piperidine (8.7 g.) and a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml). A clear solution ensued, which became turbid within 15 minutes, and an oily layer separated. Under scratching and stirring a solid mass was obtained, which was recrystallised from methanol, m.p. 130°, yield 20 g. (85%). It is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, formamide, and dimethylformamide but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 66.21; H, 7.22; N, 11.73. $C_9H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires C, 66.67; H, 7.70; N, 11.93%.)

N-(*Morpholinomethyl*)salicylamide.—To salicylamide (13.7 g.), dissolved in methanol (130 ml), was added under cooling and stirring morpholine (8.7 g.). The mixture was then treated with a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml) and left overnight at 5°. After removal of about 2/3 of the solvent, it was kept overnight at 0° and filtered. The yellow crystals obtained were recrystallised as follows. The substance (5 g.) was dissolved in hot ethyl acetate (20 ml), diluted with cyclohexane (40 ml), and cooled immediately in ice. The yellow granular crystals were filtered and washed; m.p. 125–26°, yield 9.5 g. (40%). It is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, ethyl acetate, and dioxane but insoluble in water. (Found: C, 60.46; H, 6.10; N, 11.06. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 61.02; H, 6.78; N, 11.87%.)

N-(*Pyrrolidinomethyl*)salicylamide Hydrochloride.—To salicylamide (13.7 g.), dissolved in methanol (130 ml), was added under cooling and stirring freshly distilled pyrrolidine (7.1 g.). After acidifying with HCl, the mixture was treated with a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml). Subsequent treatment was the same as above. The white crystals were removed and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 185–87° (decomp.), yield 2.8 g. (11%). It is soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, and ethyl acetate. (Found: C, 55.26; H, 6.43; N, 10.55. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_2Cl$ requires C, 56.14; H, 6.63; N, 10.91%.)

NN'-*Bis*-(*salicylamidomethyl*)piperazine.—To salicylamide (13.7 g.), dissolved in methanol (130 ml), were added under stirring piperazine hexahydrate (9.7 g., 0.05*M*) and a 38% formaldehyde solution (8 ml). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 30 minutes. On cooling in ice, the white crystals separating were recrystallised from warm methanol, m.p. 164–66° (decomp.), yield 17.5 g. (90%). It is soluble in formamide but insoluble in cold methanol, ethanol, and ethyl acetate. (Found: C, 61.95; H, 5.69; N, 14.61. $C_{20}H_{24}O_2N_4$ requires C, 62.50; H, 6.25; N, 14.58%.)

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